

The Phenomenon Of Corruption In Iraq And Its Political And Social Effects

Warqaa Muhammad Rahim

Article Info

Article History

Received:
February 28, 2022

Accepted:
September 30, 2022

Keywords :

Corruption, Structure,
Survival, Construction
And Development

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.7339597

Abstract

Corruption is a phenomenon that is inseparable from man, and it appeared with its appearance. Almost no era is devoid of manifestations of corruption, and nations always work to confront corruption because it takes them away from a righteous life and threatens society, its structure and its survival. About the destruction of the previous nations through our corruption, and we foretell the destruction of the homes of the later nations as a result of corruption. The phenomenon of corruption is one of the dangerous phenomena facing countries, especially the countries of the world of the south, including Iraq, as it began to decay in our societies, which began and the paralysis in the process of construction and development, and consequently, the inability of the state to rebuild and rebuild and build the infrastructure of the crisis for its growth. And the phenomenon of corruption in Iraq is not recent, but it increased significantly after 2003 due to the American occupation of Iraq until corruption spread in all the joints of the Iraqi state, and this is not strange because any country occupies the purpose of the occupier is to control the country's resources and spread corruption in the state in order to facilitate The process of its control and empowerment of the occupying country, but the strange thing is that Iraq is racing to obtain advanced ranks in the most corrupt country in the world according to the reports of Transparency International, as according to reports issued by Transparency International for the year 2018 that the world is divided into clean countries Very corrupt countries, clean countries, semi-corrupt countries, corrupt countries and very corrupt countries, if Iraq is occupied within the classification of very corrupt countries.

Introduction

Research Importance

The importance of this research follows, as it deals with one of the important issues, which is corruption, which has become inherent in political systems of all kinds, but in different proportions. It penetrates all state institutions to varying degrees.

Research problem

The intellectual problem of the research is embodied in answering a set of questions, which are as follows:

1. What is corruption? What are its causes, and what are its manifestations?
2. What are the social and political effects of corruption in Iraq in the (post-ISIS phase?)

Search Objective

The research aims to clarify the knowledge of the political and social effects of corruption in Iraq by knowing the reasons that led Iraq to fall within the classification of the very corrupt state.

Research Hypothesis

The research stems from the hypothesis that (the greater the percentage of corruption in institutions and in society, the greater will be its effects on many political and social aspects)

The first requirement: the concept of corruption

There are several meanings in the language for the word corruption and its derivatives, and among the most important of these meanings is "Corruption is contrary to the interest, and corrupted its wells, that is, made it corrupt, and corrupted money corruptly, taking it unjustly, corrupting against reform, corrupting people, managing and severing ties of kinship. Corruption in the English language comes from the Latin verb rumpere, meaning to break, which means that something has been broken, and this thing may be a moral or social code of conduct. In order to break this rule, it must be accurate and transparent. In terms of the concept, there are many definitions of the concept of corruption with its many aspects related to it and its different trends, depending on the different prevailing cultures and values. Johnson defines corruption as "the misuse of public office and resources by governmental parties or officials, or their use of illegal forms of political influence." In other

words, it is an informal behavior imposed by certain circumstances to which societies are exposed from time to time.

The Encyclopedia of Social Sciences defines corruption as “the misuse of public influence to achieve private profits,” and Transparency International defined corruption as “the misuse of public power to achieve private gain“. The World Bank has given its own definition of corruption in some detail, defining it as “the abuse of public office for private gain. Corruption occurs when an employee accepts, solicits, extortion or bribery to facilitate a contract or conduct a public tender, as is done when agents or intermediaries for private business companies By offering bribes to take advantage of public policies or procedures to beat competitors and make profits outside the framework of the laws in force, and corruption also occurs by exploiting the public office without resorting to bribery by appointing relatives or stealing state funds.” In the United Nations Convention against Corruption in 2003 defined corruption as Bribery in all its forms in the public and private sectors, trading in influence, abuse of public office, illicit enrichment, laundering illegal proceeds, and concealing property obtained from corruption crimes. Hington defines corruption as “one of the criteria indicating the absence of an effective political institution during the broad period of modernization witnessed by our current era.”

As for Robert Kiltgaard, he expressed corruption in the following form:

Corruption = monopoly + discretion - accountability

Transparency International has developed this formula and described it as follows:

Corruption = (monopoly + freedom of action) - (accountability + integrity + transparency)

The second requirement: manifestations of corruption

There are many forms of corruption, and these forms and manifestations cannot be fully and accurately enumerated, as it varies according to the party that practices it or the interest that it seeks to achieve. Corruption is practiced individually by the individual on a personal initiative and without coordination with individuals or other parties, and in an organized or coordinated manner. We will try to address the most prominent manifestations of corruption as follows:

1. **Bribery:** Bribery, as defined by the United Nations Convention against Corruption in Article 15 of it, means “giving a government employee undue advantages with the intent of influencing him to do or refrain from doing a certain act in the performance of his official duties.” Bribery is one of the most common forms of grand corruption, but it is also the most common form of petty corruption in the world. The realization of bribery requires interaction between the two parties (the briber and the bribe-taker), the first party represents the supply side and relates to those who are always seeking advantages, interests, rewards or gains, and the second party represents the demand side, and they are the owners of positions, influence and power who provide an advantage or preference or facilitate obtaining personal gains. There are those who go to the differentiation between positive (soft) bribery, which contributes to circumventing ineffective and routine regulations and laws and in regular ways on the one hand, and legitimizing the behavior of bribery perpetrators who wish to obtain certain deals and privileges on the other hand, and sometimes the purpose of that bribery may be to put Obstacles to importers competing in the local, so bribery will act as supply and demand, but in return, bribery may lead to a low level of quality in the service, whatever its type, or a reduction in costs in contracts and deals in order to bear the higher amount of bribery.
2. **Extortion:** Extortion differs from bribery in that it involves a party coercing another party to provide an undue benefit, usually through threats of violence, prosecution, or disclosure of harmful information. The victim of extortion may be a private person or a government official alike. In the first case, the ordinary person is left with no choice but to meet the request of the public official if he wants to obtain basic services or carry out legitimate business activities. In the second case, organized crime groups or ordinary people may obtain concessions from government officials by threatening violence or disclosing information harmful to those employees.
3. **Favoritism:** Favoritism takes the form of family, tribal or sectarian ties and partisan loyalties through the perpetuation of a certain segment of those in power regardless of the level of competence, and therefore the spread of nepotism on a large scale in a society will serve to reproduce the segments that control the functional apparatus (political, economic, security), which becomes the only beneficiary.
4. **Exploitation of influence:** It means the use of influence, whatever its source, with a public or private entity, to obtain a material or moral benefit or any specific purpose for the benefit of the offender or others, and it is equal if the source is political, functional, social or economic.

Article (18) of the United Nations Convention against Corruption defines the abuse of influence as:

1. Promising, offering or granting an undue advantage to a public official or any other person, directly or indirectly, in order to induce that public official or person to abuse his actual or assumed influence in order to obtain from an administration or public authority of the State Party an unfair advantage. owed in favor of the original instigator of that act or in favor of any other person.
2. A public official or any other person directly or indirectly soliciting or accepting any undue advantage for himself or for another person in order for that public official or person to take advantage of his actual or

assumed influence with the aim of obtaining from an administration or public authority of the State Party an undue advantage owed.

The third requirement: the causes of corruption

The researchers differed in agreeing on the classification and identification of the factors leading to corruption, and which of these factors is more influential and important than others, and this difference is due primarily to the fact that corruption is originally a human and social behavior that is affected, like other behaviors, by what is happening in the human psyche and the social environment in which motives attract and intertwine. There are reasons and complex factors.

The most important factors that lead to corruption can be identified

First, the social factors

Social and cultural factors constitute an important entry point for the emergence of the phenomenon of corruption in societies, and the rates of corruption increase for social reasons as the society develops economically and civilly, and the greater the degree of its openness to the outside world. Ingenuity or skill in obtaining wealth unjustly and by violating laws, regulations and social values, unlike those who adhere to them so that the social view of him is that he does not live in the age or does not know and does not feel the societal conditions around him or is described as stagnation.

Petrajen says: (Corruption is the main evil of our time, it reveals the ugly face everywhere, lies at the root of almost all important problems and prevents them from being solved and has devastating effects in various regions of the world and makes many millions of people suffer misery, disease, poverty and conflict and brutal forms of exploitation.

The phenomenon of corruption can spread and increase due to harmful social factors in the structure and composition of human societies and the prevailing values in them, as customs, traditions and social norms play a role in the growth of this phenomenon or uprooting it from its roots. On the other hand, the high levels of ignorance and unemployment constitute an important factor in the spread of the phenomenon of corruption. This is because the lack of cultural awareness has been linked to bribery, and the political system has played an active role in suppressing or exacerbating this phenomenon by working to build an effective administrative system and setting real and practical controls for the work of this system.

There are educational and behavioral reasons represented in the lack of interest in instilling religious values and morals in the hearts of citizens, which leads to unlimited behaviors represented in accepting bribery, lack of responsibility, and failure to respect and comply with laws.

The prevalence of social acceptance of corruption is one of the most dangerous factors. If corruption spreads in a society, this leads to a low level of loyalty to the homeland, and the individual does not realize the impact of his corrupt behavior on society and the homeland. Class disparity was and still is an important factor in the spread of administrative corruption in Iraq. There were rich and influential classes of rulers, feudalism and merchants versus poor classes of workers and peasants, which led the first classes to maintain their positions by collecting money at the expense of other classes. The process is the practice of corruption and wealth on the one hand, and poverty and lack of opportunities on the other side, where class inequality acts as a stimulant and supportive of corruption and not only a cause.

The theories of social classes assert that corruption cannot be eliminated in a society in which class conflicts prevail, because no class can influence officials in order to carry out certain actions to serve their common interests.

Second, the economic factors

Although the economic factor in its entirety intersects with the political and social factors, the purely economic character or the dominant over some variables qualifies this factor to be distinct and independent in itself, as it plays the economic aspect of the individual and society alike represented in poverty, destitution, poor income distribution, and low wages for employees. The high cost of living and the spread of unemployment play an important role in the spread of corruption. The economic reasons for the spread of corruption can be summarized as:

1. The shortage of individuals' inputs to low levels that are insufficient for living as a result of the government's lack of interest in the legislation related to the structure of wages and salaries and the failure to achieve justice in the distribution of the gross national product and achieving a balance between living requirements and wage levels is an important reason for increasing the tendencies of some individuals to achieve additional income from. Through illegal methods, as the individual may be compelled to do this work to increase his inputs by engaging in aspects of financial and administrative corruption to cover the cost of living, and cases of inflation and price hikes are other reasons that are reflected on the inputs of individuals and increase the living burdens of the individual.
2. The absence of economic effectiveness in the state, because most economic operations are suspicious business deals or resulting from brokerage operations in which financial corruption occupies a wide space, as these operations will affect the extent of the project implementation process and thus on the

production process, which will be reflected in one way or another on the level and structure of the national economy.

3. The sheer size of government projects, especially those that require large expenditures and expenses, tempt citizens aspiring to reap huge profits.
4. High levels of inflation resulting from the adoption of wrong financial policies, or a decrease in the gross national product as a result of state spending on unproductive sectors, or an increase in public spending at levels higher than normal levels, or an incorrect state budget, or an imbalance in the balance of payments, these are all reasons that will be reflected on The living capacity of the individual will constitute the appropriate ground for public and private sector employees to commit corruption.

Third: political factors

No two disagree that corruption is a phenomenon that almost no state on the face of the earth is devoid of. What concerns us is the extent of this corruption and the nature of the environment in which it occurs. Political corruption is the most dangerous type of corruption, and is considered the main cause of all cases of corruption. This is because the political decision has extended effects in all the joints and aspects of life in the state, whether social, economic or otherwise, and supporting these aspects or correcting the deviations that occur in them often begins with a political decision, and the power that the political elite possesses in practicing corruption and protecting the corrupt leads to The spread of corruption and the subjugation of junior officials to corruption, voluntarily or involuntarily, out of fear of the oppression of those in power and their obedience to their orders.

The phenomenon of corruption varies in size and degree from one society to another. Despite the presence of corruption in most societies, the environment that accompanies some types of political regimes, such as political and dictatorship regimes, encourages the emergence of the phenomenon of corruption. And its penetration is more than any other system, while the size of this phenomenon is less in democratic systems that are based on the foundations of respect for human rights and public freedoms, on political and partisan pluralism, on transparency, accountability and the rule of law.

And that authoritarian regimes see that there is a widespread phenomenon of corruption, due to the absence of democracy, the monopoly of power, and the absence of effective mechanisms and institutions in this field. Some leaders and presidents, under these ruling authoritarian regimes, surround themselves with an aura of sanctity and charisma, and examples of that are many (), and this introduces a cause. There is a direct inverse relationship between corruption and democracy, as the growth of one of them negatively affects the growth of the other, and this is reflected in political instability, as some countries, especially in developing countries, face changes in governments and ruling political systems, turning from democratic systems to dictatorship, and vice versa, which leads to the creation of Political instability, which creates the appropriate climate for the prevalence of financial and administrative corruption phenomena. These political loopholes that take place through revolutions, military coups, continuous ministerial changes, and the joining of some administrators to political parties lead to the loss of administrative bodies, and the productivity of their efficient elements and cadres, and these bodies lose their independence in Control, Accountability and Accountability.()

Political instability means temporary and changing constitutions, unstable laws, and an absence of legitimacy, which creates the atmosphere for the emergence of multiple manifestations of corruption.

The fourth requirement: the effects of corruption in Iraq (the post-ISIS phase)

Corruption is harmful and risks to the structure of society and to the political and social aspects, and the demand will be divided into two parts, the first deals with the social effects, and the second is the political effects and can be summarized:

First: The social effects of corruption in Iraq (the post-ISIS phase)

In 2014, the so-called Islamic State in Iraq and the Levant (ISIS) managed to control Fallujah and many areas in Anbar, then invaded Nineveh Governorate in northern Iraq and occupied Mosul, the capital of the province and the second largest Iraqi city. And control over some Iraqi provinces, namely Salah al-Din, Diyala, Anbar, the outskirts of Kirkuk, and even the Baghdad belt. The fall of those provinces and regions in the hands of (ISIS) prompted the population to leave their areas, as most of them live in difficult and harsh conditions, especially women and children, who have nothing to do with this conflict except that they are its victims, as the number of the displaced has reached (three and six hundred million) displaced and displaced persons).

Most international reports indicate that the living conditions of many forcibly displaced families are mostly pessimistic, as there are about four million Iraqis who lack secure food sources, and unemployment rates for the Iraqi individual (males and females), especially the internally displaced, range between (20-60%), which makes them frustrated looking for Job opportunities but to no avail(), or the displaced may be forced to work at very low wages that are not commensurate with the volume of work in the market, which leads to resentment by the labor market in the host communities. It also leads to the age groups less than 15 years entering in The labor market and school leaving to increase income, which leads to a high unemployment rate. This makes many heads of displaced families unemployed suffer from the problem of unemployment, and when we cut off sources of livelihood, the head of the displaced family cannot provide for his family members the basic

necessities that the family needs. The father feels that he is negligent towards his family. Unemployment in the future may cause negative psychological states, such as anxiety, depression, fear and insecurity, as the future becomes unknown, and in such cases, the individual is unable to form positive relationships within the family. A family between the father, his wife, and his children, in addition to the fact that the wife and children place the blame on the husband for the financial, social and psychological crisis that the displaced family suffers from, so doubts appear that are justified or unjustified between the two parties, i.e. between the husband on the one hand, and his family on the other hand. And when these doubts persist for a period of time, they turn into grudges, and perhaps hostilities that destroy the unity and cohesion of the family.

The military operations and confrontations that occurred between the organization (ISIS) and the Iraqi security forces also caused the destruction of thousands of homes in the areas occupied by the organization (ISIS), as well as the infrastructure and government institutions, in addition to the destruction of infrastructure, bridges, schools and families' homes by the organization. They differ in their beliefs and ideas, and therefore the nature of the cities has become unfit for living and there is nothing in them that encourages people to return. Some of the liberated cities are still dangerous because of the remnants of war and the explosive devices planted on the roads, in public squares and in homes that were not damaged by military operations.

Corruption also leads to the growth of an influential and wealthy group in society with the increase in poverty, which leads to an increase in class in society, and increases the percentage of the politically, economically and socially marginalized, and then leads to the migration of national talent and the inability to attract them due to the spread of corruption, which leads to weakening development Undermining its foundations and losing the educated class in society.

Corruption also leads to individuals in society feeling disrespect for the law, because they see that it protects the influential with political power, which leads to attention to private interest at the expense of the public interest, and increases the division among members of society, and the feeling of a segment of society and injustice and not obtaining its right, which is reflected on Increasing citizens' grumbling and distrust of government agencies, which leads to non-payment of taxes and evasion of them, and a lack of interest in public utilities, and consequently a decrease in state revenues and an increase in public expenditures, which leads to weak state participation in the provision of services due to the lack of sufficient revenues, or insufficient revenues for the existence of operations financial corruption in it.

Second: The political effects of corruption in Iraq

Some believe that the first reason for ISIS' entry into Iraq is the existence of political corruption, especially in the military establishment, as there was a phenomenon called (alien aliens who gave up their salaries to senior officers in exchange for their absence from the job, and stated in an investigation published by the New York Times on 23/11 /2014 about the rampant corruption in the Iraqi military and security establishment and the extent of its impact on the decline in the capabilities of the army, which was evident by the "collapse" in front of the advance of (ISIS) militants, despite the spending of billions of dollars from the Iraqi and American sides to equip and train the army and police over the past ten years, the newspaper said. "The army and police forces, due to the corruption of their leaders, collapsed in front of the advance of ISIS fighters, despite spending more than 25 billion dollars from the US government in training and arming expenses, and much more than that from the Iraqi government's treasury." Some of the weapons recently supplied by the army have ended up on the black market and in the hands of ISIS militants".

Political corruption has an impact, whether on politics, administration, or institutions. Corruption represents a serious challenge to development. On the political level, it undermines democracy and the new government by floating or even changing the course of the official process. Or corruption in elections and legislative bodies reduces accountability and distorts parliamentary representation in The political decision-making process, as for judicial corruption, it endangers the rule of law and results from the unfair distribution of services, i.e. in a broader sense, corruption erodes the institutional capacity of the government because it leads to neglect of its procedures and the depletion of its resources. Because of corruption, official positions are bought and sold, and corruption undermines the legitimacy of the government. And then the democratic values of society such as trust and tolerance.

Political corruption also leads to the weak existence of the basic service infrastructure due to the lack of resources and the inefficiency of employees, which affects the government's ability to provide basic services, and thus leads to weakening the government's legitimacy and authorities, and thus leads to increased unrest and security volatility and the consolidation of family rule, which leads to A threat to the security and stability of society.

Conclusion and recommendations

The phenomenon of corruption is a phenomenon that exists in most countries of the world, but the percentage of corruption varies in terms of spread from one country to another, according to the nature of the political system

of that country, as well as according to the system's ability to prevent and confront the phenomenon of corruption and the ways to treat it, if any.

The phenomenon of corruption in Iraq is an old phenomenon that affected most of the joints of the Iraqi state and increased to great degrees after 2003, as the job was used for personal purposes and gains, which led to the spread of the phenomenon of corruption, and this in turn led to a state of political instability in Iraq and the entry of (ISIS) elements. For some Iraqi governorates, this phenomenon has increased to the extent that Iraq has become in the advanced ranks of the most corrupt countries, according to the reports of Transparency International, and that the spread of corruption in Iraq has several causes and also has significant effects, whether these effects are political, social or economic. Therefore, the Iraqi government must take a number of measures that would reduce the phenomenon of corruption or eliminate it. These steps can be summarized as follows:

1. Creating a public opinion that rejects corruption, religiously and morally, due to its negative effects on social life and political life, and trying to gradually transform loyalty from family, clan, sect, and nationality to the values of citizenship.
2. Amending the immunity law granted to members of the House of Representatives and ministers to enable judicial authorities to investigate and be held accountable in corruption cases brought against them.
3. The necessity of completing the legal and legislative system related to combating corruption in Iraq or that limits it, such as the establishment of complementary institutions to that, for example the establishment of the (Federal Service Council), activating the role of the joint anti-corruption council, subjecting it to legal and legislative controls and making it professional, not political.
4. Activating the role of the oversight bodies in public administrations and developing the government's leadership and administrative capabilities.
5. Applying the law to everyone, whether it is a senior official in the executive, legislative or judicial authority, and not allowing any political party to interfere in favor of those against whom fraud or corruption is proven.
6. Issuing strict laws to prevent the waste of public funds and administrative corruption, and to hold them accountable seriously.

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Author Information

Dr. Warqaa Muhammad Rahim

Center for Strategic and International Studies,
University of Baghdad, Iraq
